

**FUTURE PHYSICAL CULTURE TEACHERS MECHANICS OF THE
DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE AND COMPETENCE**

**Ubaydullaev Rakhimjon,
teacher of the department "Theories of physical culture"
Ergashaliyeva Shirinoy,
student of physical culture Ferghana State University**

Annotation. The article discusses the mechanics of the development of pedagogical culture and competence of future teachers of Physical Culture. It is also reported about teaching the content of the development of pedagogical culture and competence of future teachers of Physical Culture on a scientific basis, modernizing its organizational and technological foundations.

Keywords: pedagogical culture, competence, physical education, observation, inquiry, question and answer, conversation, comparison, physical readiness, individual-psychological feature, pedagogical process.

INTRODUCTION

The scientific basis of teaching the content of the development of the pedagogical culture and competencies of future physical culture specialists, modernizing its organizational and technological foundations, and developing trends for future growth are some of the urgent issues faced by the subject "Physical Education and Sports Pedagogy." In this context, the goal of pedagogical activity is determined by society, and its result is connected with societal interests. It creates the foundation for guiding young people towards social relations and realizing the natural potential in a person to gain social experience.

Future physical culture specialists aim to develop well-rounded individuals who are strong, clear-minded, brave, patient, determined, and capable of defending the country in the future. From this perspective, innovatively organizing the activities of future physical education teachers, renewing and enriching the content of education and upbringing is of crucial importance. Along with the development of the educational process, an urgent issue of the present day is preparing future physical education teachers for innovative activities both theoretically and practically, and achieving effectiveness in physical education of the younger generation. Indeed, only physically developed and healthy individuals can fully demonstrate their intellectual and spiritual potential. In this regard, a comparative and analytical study of the historical experiences of the physical education system

in our country, along with a critical reflection on its practical experiences, provides the opportunity to organize the innovative activities of physical education teachers and identify its promising strategies. To achieve this, it is necessary to conduct targeted pedagogical research.

A modern teacher is required not only to be a deep specialist in their field but also to be well-versed in cognitive, pedagogical, and psychological aspects, possessing political and economic knowledge and innovative technologies. They must have a high level of culture and hold the title of teacher, along with the appropriate qualifications for teaching.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The development of pedagogical culture and professional pedagogical training for future physical culture specialists is aimed at comprehensive improvement through the values and potential of “Physical Education and Sports Pedagogy.” In addition to the scientific works of V.V. Borisova, I.N. Resheten, M.V. Prokhorova, A.A. Sidorov, there has been no study of the ways to form pedagogical competence in future physical education teachers up until now. In our opinion, one of the most important components in the professional activity of sports specialists is the pedagogical component. For example, in additional education (for children, adolescents, adults, etc.), sports classes with various categories require pedagogical knowledge and skill, and pedagogical methods are used to solve general physical culture problems. At the same time, the content and procedural components of the activities of physical education teachers are systematized with the use of modern innovative pedagogical technologies, which yields high results. Considering all of this, we can define the formation of pedagogical competence in future physical education teachers as one of the most important tasks in the theoretical and practical professional preparation of physical education teachers.

To develop the pedagogical culture and competence of future physical culture specialists, the seminar materials of the “Ways to Form Professional Competence of Physical Education Teachers” were tested. Additionally, the projects of “Successful Physical Education” and “Physical Education Teacher Portfolio” were introduced and tested. These projects were implemented for future physical culture specialists, introducing the “Physical Education Teacher Portfolio” and “Qualified Physical Education Teachers” programs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

During the study, we reviewed the educational documents of future physical education teachers, including their works, pedagogical practice documents, trainee diaries, and personal reports; we also examined the scientific research materials conducted during these practices. In addition, we used research methods such as observation, surveys, question-answer sessions, interviews, and comparisons.

In the process of developing the pedagogical culture and competence of future physical culture specialists, we employed methods like observation, surveys, expert evaluations, and others. Furthermore, methods of comparison and integration, statistical research methods, and conclusions were applied. To determine the initial level of pedagogical qualification of future physical education specialists, a survey was conducted among senior students in the “Physical Education and Sport” specialization.

When asked the question, “How do you understand the concept of ‘competence, qualification’?” 57% of respondents considered it as “a knowledgeable teacher,” while 13% saw it as “a highly educated teacher,” and the remaining 30% defined it as “a deep understanding of one’s profession.”

In response to the question, “How do you understand the concept of ‘Pedagogical Competence’?” none of the participants were able to give a correct answer. After this question, no one provided the correct answer to the question, “A physical education teacher’s pedagogical competence is...”. In the next question, “Identify the abilities of a qualified coach,” 54% of respondents identified “organizational” ability, 47% identified “pedagogical” ability, 42% identified “technical” ability, and 39% identified “practical” ability. The ability that scored the lowest was “constructive.”

The analysis of this survey shows that future specialists could not distinguish between the concepts of “competence,” “qualification,” and “pedagogical competence,” and they were unable to give correct and precise answers. The conclusion from this survey is that the pedagogical qualification of future specialists is insufficient, and additional research is required in this area. Therefore, we analyzed the mandatory education standards for the “Physical Education and Sport” specialization in relation to the research tasks. During the process of studying normative documents, methods of theoretical analysis, synthesis, and comparison were applied, which highlighted the differences in the direction of the physical education teachers' professional-pedagogical competence development.

During the experimental phase of the research, the level of pedagogical competence of 2nd to 4th-year students, sports coaches, and physical education teachers was assessed, and the method of using person-centered technologies was tested as one of the ways to form this essential professional attribute. During the formative experiment, various projects focused on competencies were implemented, such as "Trainee Portfolio," "Teacher Portfolio," "Qualified Physical Education" projects, and others. The theoretical model was tested as a measure during special assignments conducted in the course of the experiment. The result showed that the pedagogical competence level of the students in the experimental groups had increased.

CONCLUSION

In today's context, it is necessary to organize physical education lessons through modern methodologies, emphasizing not only physical exercises but also psychological preparation, directing and distributing mental energy, and incorporating psychological-pedagogical methods into the process. This is because today, focusing on students' physical preparedness, health, and body composition can show their signs of maturity and health.

The role of the pedagogical team is crucial in preparing future physical education teachers for professional pedagogical activities. Improving the quality of education leads to better living standards across all sectors of society. Since introducing innovations is an effective means of enhancing education quality, developed countries continuously try to introduce innovations into their educational processes.

In the future, physical education teachers will rely on physical qualities such as strength, speed, agility, endurance, and perseverance in their professional activities. These physical qualities are always interconnected and manifest together, explaining the internal integrity of the human body and the interaction of its functions.

REFERENCES

1. Борисова Н.В. Педагогические особенности создания и внедрения системы активных методов обучения в институте повышения квалификации: Автореф. дис. . канд.пед.наук. М., 1987. - 23с.; Решетень Н.Н., Прохорова М.В., Фомин Ю.А. Деловые игры в подготовке специалистов по физической культуре и спорту: Методические разработки.

- М.: ГЦОЛИФК, 1983. - 37 с.; Прохорова Т.Н. Теория и практика формирования творческой личности учащегося в системе художественно-эстетического образования : диссертация ... доктора педагогических наук : 13.00.01. - Москва, 2003. - 301 с.; Сидоров А.А., Прохорова М.В., Синюхин Б.Д.
2. Педагогика: Учебник для студентов, аспирантов, преподавателей и тренеров по дисциплине «Физическая культура». М.: Терра спорт, 2000. - 272 с.
3. Мамадова, Ф. (2023). Bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat mutaxassislarining pedagogik madaniyati va kompetensiyasini takomillashtirishning pedagogik modeli. Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 3(7), 266-272.
4. Tursinovich, K. A., Mirzaakhmadovna, M. F., & Alijonovich, E. T. (2022). 'Topical issues of pre-university preparation of students in the field of physical culture and sports. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 7, 253-255.
5. Qayumovna, R. M. (2021). Examining and monitoring of the impact of hypo dynamic factors on the state of physical fitness in students. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices, 3, 40-43.